

User Research Methods:

Distinctive Need Expressions from an In-depth Interview and a Generative Method

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to explore the differences of two user research methods. It compares traditional in-depth interview to human-centered generative tools. The former is based on what people say and think and the latter is based on what people make and create. The research theme was housewives' needs for their kitchens. Two groups of five housewives in their 30s participated in the study. The differences of the two methods were analyzed by comparing the results in terms of quantity and quality of the needs. The in-depth interview produces relatively more detailed experienced problems and negative feelings in users' specific contexts than the generative tools. Conversely, the generative method produces relatively more future-oriented ideas by revealing wishes and dreams. Consequently, it tends to produce more positive feelings about the research theme. The results imply that the in-depth interview is a desirable method when designers have little information about the design problem. In contrast, applying generative tools will be more effective when designers need to get design insights from users. It is suggested that the two methods are complementary, rather than alternative, for understanding multi-levels of users' needs more clearly and for obtaining practical design insights.

Keywords: *user research method, in-depth interview, generative tools, user needs*

1. Introduction

The focus of design has shifted toward user-oriented design process. This shift is based on today's market place, one full of competitive products and smart users. Product success depends on proper designs reflecting users' needs more quickly and accurately than other competitors do. This means the market driving force is moving towards the user side and transforms current users from passive decision-makers with firmly established alternatives, to active informers expressing needs to design partners as a seed for product development. Today's users have more influential capabilities for successful product design than any other subjects do. Techniques and methods capturing their needs become important in design fields for market success.

Any of the methods applied in user research are based on communication between designers and users. Communication differs qualitatively among selected methods, because users can express their needs within the range supported by the selected method. Some methods are more effective than others in capturing more needs or to clarify concrete needs, even if a user expresses his/her needs at the same level. Therefore, it is critical to

apply an appropriate method for designers when they want to fully understand users' needs.

User research methods approaching user needs are in a range of ways. Traditional researches have focused on verbal and observational methods. The verbal methods are based on what people say and think. They provide information in words within their perception of experience. The observational methods reveal what people do and use giving just observable information [1]. As there is more than what can be revealed by words and activities, it is necessary to access the deeper levels of tacit and latent needs. To appreciate those needs, make methods access what the users feel, dream, and imagine by analyzing what users create with the given toolkits. Make methods enable designers not only to get more information that cannot be revealed in words and behavior but also to resonate with users in participatory ways.

It is not useful just to give insights to designers that emphasize the importance of participatory methods. Rather, distinctive insights from different methods must be considered for more effective user-oriented design, so that designers are able to select the most relevant method to their design circumstances by a thorough comparison. From this viewpoint, we applied the in-depth interview and the generative tools to compare a conventional method to a human-centered method.

The purpose of this study is to provide implications for designers in need of user research. This paper attempts an exploratory study to compare the in-depth interview, as a verbal method, and the generative tools, as a participatory make method. The main concern of this paper is to find the relative advantages of the two methods in revealing users' needs. It will be valuable to identify distinctive implications among methods, since product designers can refer to the results as a guide when choosing a method for their user research.

2. Needs research methods

Current market circumstance has motivated user-centered design to occupy a critical role in the product design field to realize users' needs with the appropriate product. This shift is reasonable when it comes to Archer's definition of design; design begins with a need, which involves a design problem [2]. The primary goal of product design is developing products to satisfiers of human needs, which rests on designers' capability to understand those needs. As designers are concerned with users' needs, the effort to know how to catch those needs is crucial for designers in the process of new product development. Designers conduct an expanded role to study their potential users, and begin to focus on user research methods.

A user research method is a kind of language for communicating between designers and users. It is essential to select an appropriate method for effective communication: one that emphasizes more comparative studies of user research methods to accumulate knowledge to guide the adoption of the most suitable method. Designers have to know not only what methods will be possible and suitable for their specific case but also to anticipate the content quality of the method they choose.

2.1. Traditional method: In-depth interview

The ways designers and design researchers traditionally use to access needs ranged across social science

techniques, such as surveys, interviews, focus group, and observations [3, 4, 5, 6]. The purpose of these methods is to gather useful information from users [7]. They are adopted not only in the academic field but also in practical marketing and design fields. We adopt the in-depth interview from these conventional methods.

The interview is one of the most widely used qualitative methods [8]. Interview as a qualitative approach focuses on the nature of things, while a quantitative approach deals with an amount of something [9]. The purpose of interviewing is to enter into the other person's perspective that is meaningful, knowable, and able to be made explicit [8]. The response from the interviewee is related to the question of 'what is' in contrast to the survey response, for instance, on what are their experiences and expectations.

The interview method depends on verbal expression of respondents, sometimes tackled by the capability of respondents to express their thought in words. It usually seriously limits the scope for imagination. It is a weakness of traditional methods weighing verbal communication. Some studies [10, 11, 12, 13] point out that this weakness is critical, because the hidden needs of which users cannot talk are sometimes more important factors to develop innovative products than any other needs in words. From this viewpoint, some methods to overcome the limitation of verbal methods have been developed. Such methods include cultural probes, generative tools, and contextmapping in the participatory design field.

2.2. Human-centered method: Generative Tools

The traditional methods are limited to the needs being depicted linguistically or observed visually. They are deficient in accessing tacit and latent needs that cannot be articulated [6, 14, 15, 16]. Raising those limitations of conventional methods, the new tools for design research have been introduced, especially for the participatory design field. The new methods inspiring the design team in the early phases tend to involve users in generative research. These include cultural probes [10], generative tools [17], and contextmapping [18]. While the traditional methods offer a view on the current and past experiences, the new tools for participatory design provide a view to reveal latent needs and future states [18, 19]. These techniques focus on what people make with 'toolkits.' This helps researchers catch participants' tacit and latent needs.

The generative tools technique is a human-centered method with a design-led and participatory minded perspective [20]. The techniques require everyday people to participate in early stages of the design process and create new design ideas by enabling them to reveal their own latent needs and dreams. Participants make their own artifacts containing their needs with toolkits provided by researchers such as words, images, or drawing materials [19]. Participants project their own aspirations onto the artifacts in the forms of collages, maps, stories, plans, and/or memories [12].

3. Research design

This study compares two methods, each of traditional and human-centered methods. The traditional one is the in-depth interview, one of the most widely used methods. It enables researchers to understand what the subjects need and why it is important to them. The human-centered approach is the generative tools that encourage

participants' involvement in the fuzzy front end of product design, boosting collective creativity.

The overall research design is not as tight as the usual comparative experiment. This is an exploratory study to seek implications by searching the notable distinctiveness of each method. The main interest is to explore how different the outcomes are from the two methods by focusing on the distinguishing characteristics of the results. Researchers tried to grasp a holistic understanding of methodological significance based on the distinctive strengths of each result. The primary conditions of the two cases are controlled by the research theme and basic characteristics of the participants.

3.1. Theme

The theme for the user research was the kitchen. It includes several issues, such as the structure of kitchen space and the attributes and the arrangement of kitchen furniture. The criteria selection themes are availability and usability for most people, familiarity for usage, and regularity for use pattern in everyday life. The kitchen is not a special item for most people, but a familiar and routine item used frequently in everyday life. Many user needs will exist at the unconscious level, this being a good way to observe patterns of needs by each method.

3.2. Participants

Research participants were recruited to balance their age, educational level, and working hours in a kitchen. All the participants are housewives, for it is desirable to recruit frequent kitchen users. Five housewives in their 30s were recruited for each method. Their basic characteristics are shown in <Table 1>. The interviewees' ages range from 31 to 39 and those of the generative tools participants' from 32 to 39. All participants were college graduates with bachelors' degrees. The interviewees and generative tools participants work in their kitchens from 2.8 hours to 2.6 hours a day and have family members of 3.0 to 2.8 on average, respectively.

Table 1. Characteristics of the participants

	In-depth interview	Generative Tools
Average age	34.8	34.4
Education	College graduates	College graduates
Average working hours in the kitchen per day	2.8 hours	2.6 hours
Average number of family members	3.0	2.8

4. Methods

4.1. In-depth interview

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face for five days from January 4th to 8th, 2010. It was a semi-structured interview with several leading questions. A well-trained interviewer led the overall progress with both prepared and instant questions corresponding to the participants' responses. As each leading question progressed, the interviewer asked additional questions to elicit necessary information or when the response was insufficient.

Participants were invited to a seminar room in our university with a brief notification of the theme. First, they were asked to introduce themselves and describe their kitchen as an icebreaker. The initial questions started with

broad topics about working experiences in the kitchen, and afterwards narrowed to specific topics related to structure or kitchen furniture. The interview with each participant took about two hours. The interview was voice-recorded with the participants' approval.

4.2. Generative Tools

The generative method was conducted with a group of five people. It took nine days including workbook completion days and a group session from December 29th, 2009 to January 6th, 2010. This method was largely separated into two stages; one to complete a workbook, as an immersion stage: the other to participate in the group session. The immersion stage is an individual activity to sensitize participants to the research theme. The participants accomplished one of seven special tasks each day and two daily tasks for a week.

The special tasks include describing troublesome matters, working experiences, and introducing one's know-how in the kitchen. These tasks trigger the participants to think about their needs. The daily tasks were given in common for a week. These were to take pictures and keep a kitchen diary. These tasks detail their daily experiences. The pictures below are of a kitchen diary and a special task output.

Figure 1. Common task: Kitchen diary

Figure 2. Special task: Storing kitchenware

After completing the workbook stage, participants had a group session. Before the group session, participants had an individual pre-interview about their workbook. They explained how they did their workbook by date and some questions followed their storytelling for more detailed explanation. In the first step of the group session, they made a collage to express their dream kitchen with 156 words, 36 symbols, and 132 images. Their artifacts were shown to other participants and explained thoroughly. In the next step, they made scale kitchen models from toy blocks and colored clay on a three-dimensional structure with sticky walls. They participated in storytelling regarding their modeling afterwards. The entire process was video-recorded, with some scenes captured in photos, by agreement. The group session steps are shown in <Table 2>.

As indicated in <Table 3>, the in-depth interview produces only verbal expression, while the generative method produces not only verbal but also 2D and 3D creative expression. Time spent in expressing each participant's response varies with the method as in the table.

Table 2. Group session for the generative tools

Table 3. Summary of the implementations of the two methods

Meeting type		In-depth interview	Generative Tools	
		Individual	Group	Individual*
Approximate run time (min)		120	100	45
Average time per person by expression type (min)	Introduction and questionnaire	30	30	45
	Speaking	90	10	
	2D Making		30	
	3D Modeling		30	

* Individual pre-interview about the workbook before the group session

5. Results

The in-depth interviews and storytelling of generative tools were transcribed. We then conducted content analysis. At the first step of analysis, reading both transcripts several times, researchers extracted as many meaningful needs as possible. The extracted needs were classified into several issues. The needs were not only sorted by similarity of issues but also structured by characteristics of expression. All the analysis steps were cross-checked with our two colleagues.

The differences of the two methods become explicit with respect to verbal expression characteristics. The characteristics of needs expression were identified by two analysis criteria as shown in <Figure 3>. First, the users' needs expressions are based on either positive or negative feelings. The needs based on negative feelings are related to the problems they have experienced. Conversely, the needs in positive expression include users' general thoughts and specific ideas. The positively expressed needs are divided again into two levels of detail by the groups of abstract needs and concrete needs. Prior to the analysis by the two criteria, the number of expressed needs of the two methods was compared. In sum, the distinctive features are quantity of the whole needs and issues, emotional expression, and concreteness of needs. These differences create distinct implications for designers. Thus, when they study users, it is valuable to compare methods' specific qualities based on what aspects they need to know in the circumstances.

Figure 3. Analysis criteria

5.1. Abundance of expressed needs

The needs extracted from the two methods are counted to compare the abundance of needs expression. Similar needs were included in the total amount, because they had different contexts leading to different solutions. The quantity of the expressed needs represents the capability of a method in which a participant can approach wide ranging issues about a theme. The entire needs sets from the two methods were differed, as shown in <Table 4>.

Table 4. Comparative numbers of expressed needs and issues

		In-depth interview		Generative tools	
Total number of expressed needs		293	100%	176	100%
Positive feeling-based needs	Number of abstract descriptions	136 (46.4%)	55.6%	78 (44.3%)	64.8%
	Number of concrete suggestions	27 (9.2%)		36 (20.5%)	
Negative feeling-based needs	Number of problems	130	44.4%	62	35.2%
Average number of needs per minute of personal speaking		3.26		3.20	
Total number of expressed issues		51		39	

The entire number includes what the participants said about their problems, feelings, thoughts, and ideas. The in-depth interviews revealed 293 needs, while the generative tools revealed 176. However, since the total contact time for each method differed, the count of needs must be converted by the time unit for a fair comparison. This comparison shows that there is no difference in the discovery rate of the needs between the two methods. That is, the different counts are due to the different duration of the two methods.

The needs are classified into groups grounded in the same issues. When the number of issues presented in the two cases is compared, 51 issues arise in the in-depth interviews and the generative tools yield 39. This provides information of user contexts that imply various facets of needs for a solution.

There is little difference in total count with a time unit but the in-depth interviews yield more detail results than the generative tools in a specific user context. The in-depth interview makes the interviewees more inspired to talk about their experiences using narratives than does the generative method. Those experiences reveal more detailed facets of one's context of a kitchen with many similar needs. The in-depth interview method enables designers to learn about user experiences based on more specific user context.

The generative method has other outcomes from the participants besides verbal expressions. The generative tools allow participants to make what they want based on their experiences. Thus, participants do not say so much about their experience in words, but their thoughts, experiences, and needs are expressed by making artifacts, i.e. collages or clay models. That is why there are fewer verbally expressed needs than in the in-depth interviews. This inspires the designer to generate holistic design ideas.

The two methods differ in the contents in the substance of their results, implying that each method has its advantages. Designers can select the more appropriate method to obtain the richer consequence, based on these differences. The in-depth interview gives a narrative user experience, bridging the gap between users and designers. Therefore, it is recommended that designers choose the in-depth interview method when they have to

understand the concrete circumstances concerning a design problem. That is, interviewing users is more fruitful when designers do not have clear design solutions due to lack of information about the design issue.

Conversely, the generative method has an impact on designers' inspiration more directly than does the in-depth interview method, because it has tangible outputs that are sensed that contain intuitive messages from users. When designers search for more practical ideas, the outputs of the generative tools can be a trigger to develop design ideas. Comparing the richness of the expressed needs generated from the two methods, it seems beneficial to conduct a previous in-depth interview if designers do not have enough information involving design issues, such as user experiences, and concrete usage circumstances.

5.2. Emotional expression of the needs

There is another difference regarding the ways of needs expression. When the participants expressed their needs, they also expressed their feelings that are related to the needs. The expressed needs contained both negative and positive feelings. Even if someone expresses the same need, the ways to express them can be different, such as 'I hope to' or 'Something annoys me.' When approaching a design problem, it is as important to know critical problems users experience, so as to catch users' wants, because both sides of reducing one's inconvenience and improving one's benefit can be the starting points for design.

The in-depth interviews generated 130 negative feeling-based needs and 163 positive feeling-based needs. Conversely, the generative tools had fewer negative-based expressions (62 negative and 114 positive ones). The generative tools extracted relatively more positive feelings than did the in-depth interviews.

The needs based on positive feeling expression focus on a desirable future state. Most ideas or suggestions for the future were more likely expressed in a positive manner. Especially, the participants using generative tools tended to focus on futuristic ideas. In contrast, the negative ones were more likely related to past experiences and current problem situations. The participants expressed their inconvenience, dissatisfaction, and unpleasant situations. The in-depth interviews have a greater proportion of negative expressions, because the interviewees mostly concentrated in narrating their unfavorable experiences. In addition, it could be influenced by the meeting types of the two methods. The group session of the generative tools may preclude the participants from opening ones' troubles, since they might worry about how the others may feel about them. Those negative feelings can inspire designers to develop a product that can solve the problems.

Both sides of the expressional manners will provide different insights for designers. It can be argued that the application of the complementary methods will be beneficial to learn the whole spectrum of users' circumstances, problematic matters, and feelings. This enables designers to get closer to a satisfactory design in the user context with various aspects of needs.

5.3. Level of detail

The positively expressed needs from the two methods are not only classified into homogeneous issues but also sorted by the detail level of expression. The depth of needs is in contrast to their abundance. If users can express their needs in detail, designers can adopt those needs as design ideas. Then the design would impress the users

more favorably, because the communication gap between users and designers had been closed. It is important to derive more detailed needs from the participants to approach what they really want.

The detail levels are divided into two groups: abstract descriptions of needs and concrete suggestions. When participants mentioned their experience or problems without any solutions or ideas, and gave a general attribute, these needs were counted as an abstract description of their needs. In contrast, the concrete suggestions include mentioning a specific shape, function, or style.

While the abundance of needs was higher in the in-depth interviews, the concreteness of needs expression was lower in the interviews. Twenty-seven concrete suggestions were extracted from the in-depth interviews despite the abundance of total needs. The interviewees expressed a greater number of needs but focused on their troublesome experiences without imagining a possible solution. They were asked to describe their dream kitchen, yet they suggested fragmentary improvement, fixated on their present problems that include, for example, changing materials of the sink cover or changing the way of opening the storage door.

Conversely, 36 concrete suggestions were taken from the results of the generative tools. Saying what they need and want, the participants conceived their dream kitchen. They could articulate their needs more clearly than was the case for the interviewees, even describing and visualizing specific functions and structures of the kitchen furniture and devices. The generative method supports the participants with tangible toolkits, so they can find ways to explain their thoughts visually and physically. It was unnecessary to ask them to describe their dream kitchen, since they already intended to express not only by saying but by also making.

The difference becomes obvious when comparing the ratios of concrete suggestions to total needs. The in-depth interviews have 9.2% concrete suggestions from the needs expressed, and the generative tools have 20.5% of the total. That is, the in-depth interviews have less power to inspire the participants to elaborate what they need, despite eliciting more abundant needs than did the generative tools. However much they could express their needs, it would be more beneficial to catch concrete suggestions from the user. This would enable design teams to start from a clear design concept.

This comparison signifies that participants were immersed in the theme with different levels, influencing their capability to imagine and express possible solutions by themselves. Most of the interviewees could not explain how their problem could be resolved. One of the reasons is that they do not have any supportive tools to imagine and express their needs beyond verbal expression. Not only this, but also it is natural that the in-depth interview method has a weakness to approaching developed ideas due to the lack of a prior immersion stage, unlike the generative tools method. That the participants of the generative tools had 7-day workbook activities means they had more opportunities to think about the theme. Although less elaborative ideas were extracted when compared to the generative tools, the in-depth interview method is a good way to scan broad user experience.

Some examples of needs extracted from the two methods are shown in <Table 5>. In abstract descriptions, all the participants express desirable states from the overall viewpoint. Especially, the interviewees tended to express needs based on their experience, which shows their specific context. The participants of the generative tools attempted more to give an outline of their ideas.

In concrete suggestions, the interviewees more focused on improvement of the present status, whereas the

participants of the generative tools tried to devise new things. The concrete suggestions from the generative tools were mainly extracted from their 3D models. It is because the participants of the generative tools had to make tangible artifacts containing their ideas and dreams. They made what they wanted and explained the functions and details with their rough models.

On the problem side, all the participants expressed their inconvenience in the kitchen. There is no striking difference except the amount of expressions. The problems expressed by the generative tools were mostly revealed in the 2D collage. The participants expressed their negative experiences with negative words, symbols, and images. Some of the participants made their collages by dividing sections for positive and negative aspects.

Table 5. Examples of the expressed needs of the two methods

		In-depth interview	Generative tools
Positive feeling-based needs	Abstract descriptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ I want to see all the stored kitchenware in one glance. I always have trouble finding the things I need. ♦ I wish I could store my kitchenware in places where they are not seen. That way it will be easier for me to clean the kitchen. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ I think my kitchen would be a more enjoyable place if I were able to share the space with others, like having a party. ♦ I need places to put food or unfinished dishes while cooking. It would be nicer to make temporary spaces rather than fixed ones
	Concrete suggestions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ I need a foldable draining board under the kitchen cabinet. ♦ Partitioned doors for kids will be useful. There are too many dangerous things in the kitchen. ♦ Various forms of door will be better, for example, accordion doors, sliding doors, or button-opening doors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ It will be useful to open the cabinet doors with a soft nudge when I have things in my hand. ♦ I need a machine that can give me directions when I come into the kitchen. It manages everything from planning the menu to giving know-how in the kitchen.
Negative feeling-based needs	Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ I worry that my kitchen will seem too messy to others. ♦ My sink is too small to wash a big saucepan. ♦ It is inconvenient to take out stacked pans. ♦ I don't have a place to store foods that need to be stored at room temperature. So, I just cram them in the refrigerator. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ I'm so bored when I am cooking or washing dishes by myself. ♦ Upper cabinets are not so useful because they are too high. ♦ I feel uncomfortable when using stored dishes even if they had been just washed.

5.4. Emotional dimensions in user experience

Emotional aspects are subdivided by dimensions in user experience. Using their kitchens, users experience various emotions accompanying with their experiential context. It means that the kitchen can be an emotionalized place beyond its functional usage. As shown in <Figure 4>, the emotional experiences can be divided into 2 x 2 dimensions by two axes: finality and orientation of the experience.

Figure 4. Dimensions of the emotional experiences

First, the emotional experiences can be divided by the finality of experience. Considering the kitchen as a means for accomplishing another purpose, users experience extrinsic emotions, such as saving his/her face. On the contrary, users feel intrinsic emotions when their experience within the kitchen itself is purposeful, such as having fun. Second, the emotional experiences can also be divided by the orientation of experience such that the experiences are either self-oriented or others-oriented. The self-oriented is experiences related to the user him/herself, such as confirming one's role in the kitchen. The others-oriented is using the kitchen for relationship with others, such as sharing ceremonial meanings with others by using the kitchen. The two dimensions of the emotional user experiences can be cross-wised as in <Table 6>.

Table 6. Emotional user experience

Orientation \ Finality	Extrinsic	Intrinsic
Self-oriented	Role confirmation	Having fun
		Aesthetic appreciation
Others-oriented	Social gathering	Ceremonial
	Face saving	

The first cell, role confirmation is the extrinsic and self-oriented emotional user experience. Some participants identify themselves when using their kitchen. It means that they confirm their role by associating themselves with their kitchen. For example, one of the participants said that she feels herself as meaningful when she can do something for her family in the kitchen. This kind of emotional experience goes beyond the intrinsic user experience in the kitchen because using the kitchen is regarded as a means of identifying oneself. This experience is not related to others but links between one's self to the kitchen.

The second cell, social gathering and face saving are the extrinsic and others-oriented emotional experiences. These experiences focus on the relationship with family, friends, and significant others. The participants wanted to change their kitchen as a café-like space in which they could have a party or chat away with friends. On the other hand, they were anxious about what their kitchen would look like. Some participants feel forced to clean up their kitchen always because of concerns of losing faces.

The third cell contains having fun and aesthetic appreciation, which is the intrinsic and self-oriented emotional user experience. Some of the participants said that they need an entertainment space in their kitchen. Apart from the original functions of the kitchen, they just want to enjoy the place. Also, some of them want to transform their kitchen as an art gallery where they can appreciate works of art. This experience is not related to others but to themselves for enjoying their kitchen.

The last cell, ceremonial experience is the intrinsic and others-oriented emotional experience. This experience is captured from the generative tools participants. They regard their kitchen as a place for performing a ceremony by harmonizing family members. One of the participant said that she wants her kitchen to have a relaxing atmosphere with a warm heart because she considers mealtime as a ceremony for her family. The point of this experience is the kitchen is a priceless place for one's family. The kitchen is a symbolic place which can bring

home to users the meaning of the time with family members and can make them share warmth.

According to these criteria, the needs from the two methods are classified. The in-depth interview had 63 emotional needs, while the generative tools had 47 emotional needs, as shown in <Table 7>. The emotional user experiences are distinctively distributed between the two methods. The interviewees are more concerned about losing face that they expressed 23 out of 63. This result is interpreted in the same context that is the reason why the interviewees said more negative feeling-based needs. The interviewees are more concentrated on their problems at the moment. On the other hand, the participants of the generative tools expressed more experiences of having fun in their kitchen, 23 out of 47. They could think about more creative use of their kitchen beyond its original function.

Table 7. Comparative numbers of the emotional user experiences

Criterion 1: Finality						Criterion 2: Orientation
Extrinsic	In-depth (N=63)	Generative Tools (N=47)	Intrinsic	In-depth (N=63)	Generative Tools (N=47)	
Role confirmation	5(7.9%)	2(4.3%)	Having fun	13(20.6%)	23(48.9%)	Self-oriented
			Aesthetic appreciation	20(31.8%)	10(21.3%)	
Social gathering	2 (3.2%)	5(10.6%)	Ceremonial	0(0%)	3(6.4%)	Others-oriented
Face saving	23(36.5%)	4(8.5%)				

6. Discussion

The traditional user research methods are generally adopted to investigate users' needs, despite their restricting user participation. It is fair in general to apply marketing research methods to the product design field. Few attempts have investigated user research methods for the sake of product design. As users have critical roles in design fields, selecting the appropriate method to study users is a current issue in the design field. The methods applied for user research, being the first step of product design, should be carefully selected, because each method may have distinctive contexts of research leading to different outcomes. This affects successful design.

From this viewpoint, the study explored differences between the in-depth interview and the generative method to guide designers to select an appropriate user research method. It is insufficient to detect the general advantages and disadvantages of each method. Rather, it is valuable to clarify the different characteristics of the methods and to determine which method would best contribute to a particular design issue. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to amplify the knowledge about the two methods. This means dimensions and categories of housewives' needs from the two methods are not the focus of this study. They will be explored in the next stage.

The methods compared in this study have their distinct qualities. First, the in-depth interviews have more abundant results of concrete experiences in a specific context than do the generative tools. That is, the in-depth interview is useful to check the overall topics as the inception of the user research. The in-depth interview

method is an informative way that allows designers to think about the possible issues related to the design problem. It would be a meaningful preparatory research when designers do not have sufficient information about the design problem or the users.

Second, the participants expressed their needs with both positive and negative feelings. In the in-depth interview method, more negative feelings were expressed focusing on saying what they have experienced until now, whereas the generative method has more future-oriented insights. The emotional difference implies two-edged solutions to the design problem. Designers not only have to meet users' positive expectations by improving positive manners but also must remove negative factors from the users' circumstances. Therefore, it is recommended to apply complementary methods to reveal both futuristic insights and one's negative aspects.

Third, the participants could express relatively concrete needs through the generative tools because they were able to make more tangible artifacts to reveal their needs and also spent more time to do their workbooks. While the in-depth interviews involved broad issues with superficial needs, the needs expressed in the generative tools include highly elaborated design ideas. Thus, it can lead to direct inspirations for the designers. The generative method is an immediate way to apply ideas to the design, while the in-depth interview method is more of a preparatory informative approach. Therefore, if designers take their design direction with sufficient information, it could be useful to adopt this approach to generate more immediate and detailed ideas.

Fourth, the emotional experiences are subdivided into four dimensions by two axes: finality and orientation of the experience. The dimensions are extrinsic and intrinsic experience by the finality axis and self-oriented and others-oriented experience by the orientation axis. The emotional experiences are differently derived from the two methods. The interviewees worried about losing face because they focused on their present problems when they expressed their needs. On the other hand, the participants of the generative tools expressed more experiences of having fun by using the kitchen. It means that they could expand their thoughts from the original use to more creative way of using the kitchen. This result shows that the generative tools make the participants express more expanded experiences. Designers can catch more user experiences beyond the present problems from the generative tools, which enables them to design broader user experiences than using the in-depth interview only.

There is no royal road to researching users suited to all the design cases. One should consider the method that would be effective in a particular design case, because the result of user research can be discriminative based on the application of a specific method. More attempts and efforts to explore methodological differences are needed. These will form a basis for user research principles. It will support designers, leading the user-centered design field to be more perfectly user-oriented.

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